

Explore what *Investigating in Science* could look like to learn more about the Planet Earth and Beyond. (Table adapted from Fenton, 2011)

	Modelling	Classifying and Identifying	Pattern seeking	Making things or developing systems	Observing	Fair testing (scientific method)
This could be...	<input type="checkbox"/> Learn about limestone caves and chemistry – make your own stalagmites and stalactites . <input type="checkbox"/> Create a story (words, role play, video animation, cartoons) that link familiar everyday concepts to explain, eg, where does the sun go at night, what makes the moon shine? <input type="checkbox"/> Make a model solar system with planets that really float above the table! <input type="checkbox"/> Try this interactive solar system to arrange the planets in order from the sun <input type="checkbox"/> Make a model volcano that erupts <input type="checkbox"/> Get students to act out planet orbits to scale on the playing field <input type="checkbox"/> Use a ball and a lamp to investigate if the Earth would still experience seasons if it was NOT tilted on its axis <input type="checkbox"/> Use a lamp and a ball to explore the phases of the moon from the perspective of the Earth. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> The interactive planets . What are some features that could help you identify the planets of our solar system? <input type="checkbox"/> Learn how to make plaster casts of animal tracks or make “fossils” for your students to identify <input type="checkbox"/> Viewing and sharing ideas about a significant rock formation in their area <input type="checkbox"/> Collecting a variety of rock samples and writing a classification key to identify them <input type="checkbox"/> Use a key to identify different cloud types <input type="checkbox"/> Learn to recognise the constellations and other features of the night sky. <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring changes in shadows over a period of time to show change in the position of the Sun <input type="checkbox"/> The interactive planets . Can you find what the first four planets have in common? <input type="checkbox"/> Plot the distribution and magnitude of recorded earthquakes in New Zealand <input type="checkbox"/> Discuss the types of evidence used in determining past positions of continents <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the changing spatial relationships of the Earth, its moon, and the Sun, and the way different cultures have used these patterns to describe and measure time, and position, <i>e.g.</i> , <i>phases of the Moon, eclipses, tides, seasons, sun clocks</i> ; <input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/> Build a sun projector as a safe way to study a star in the daytime. Photograph sunspots and watch the transit of Venus. <input type="checkbox"/> Making a simple needle compass and demonstrating how it is used <input type="checkbox"/> Make a simple data logger for \$10. Use it to test for UV radiation from the sun or turn an LED into a solar cell. <input type="checkbox"/> Explore energy efficiency using the Earth's resources – EnviroPower school project <input type="checkbox"/> Research how other famous scientists made discoveries 'by luck' (serendipity) <input type="checkbox"/> Create a simple science game or simulator (Mac and PC). <input type="checkbox"/> Build an air track to simulate the frictionless environment of space. Push the model spaceship and it goes and goes...	<input type="checkbox"/> Draw pictures to show the activities that students do at different times over a twenty-four hour period <input type="checkbox"/> Prepare a report or interview schedule on traditional Maori weather forecasting <input type="checkbox"/> Observe weathering and erosion over a period of time <input type="checkbox"/> Observe the types of cloud that are associated with different types of weather <input type="checkbox"/> Over the course of a year, observe where the sun sets or rises. <input type="checkbox"/> Observe the night sky and observe how the planets and stars move across the sky. <input type="checkbox"/> Use a planetarium programme to find the position of planets and then go and look for them in the sky <input type="checkbox"/> Collect micro-meteorites and find the best time of year to collect them. What do they look like under a microscope?	<input type="checkbox"/> Fair testing method <input type="checkbox"/> Deciding if a project is technology or science <input type="checkbox"/> Launching water-powered, plastic soft drink bottle “rockets” with a bike pump and testing variables which affect the flight of such model rockets <input type="checkbox"/> Does the weather have an effect on human emotions?

Notes:

- The above are a few suggestions only. Please add to this document and save it for your own use on your home computer if you find it useful.
- Observations could be recorded digitally if appropriate; sounds, time lapse still images or motion video clips.
- Observational drawings are to be scientific observational drawings, with no shading. Dots and lines are allowed. The drawing must be done in pencil on A4 paper, with the specimen's name(s) printed in the lower left corner. It should be drawn directly from the observed object(s). A scale must be shown. (from [Taranaki Science Fair website](#))
- Investigations using animals must follow the guidelines outlined in this site [Caring for Animals](#) and the Animal Welfare Act 1999
- Investigations that involve practical work must follow health and safety guidelines as set out in this document [‘Safety and Science Guidance Manual’](#)